

A Study of Predictive Value of Endometrial Thickness, Morphology and Vasculature on Outcome after IUISuchitra Pasupula¹, R. Umadevi², Vanukuru Jayasree³, Salicheemala Bhuvaneshwari⁴, T. Lakshmi Suseela⁵¹Postgraduate, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Sri Venkateswara Medical College, Tirupathi,^{2,3}Assistant professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Sri Venkateswara Medical College, Tirupati,⁴Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Sri Venkateswara Medical College, Tirupati⁵Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Government Medical College, Kadapa

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: “Infertility is the inability of a couple to achieve pregnancy over an average period of one year (in a woman under 35 years of age) or 6 months (in a woman above 35 years of age) despite adequate, regular (3-4 times per week), unprotected sexual intercourse. A complete infertility work up is done before a treatment plan can be developed. The work up is streamlined, focused and completed shortly so that treatment can be started expeditiously. The success depends on age, duration and type of infertility, follicular count, semen quality and endometrial receptiveness. Studies on endometrial parameters in IUI cycles are insufficient to predict their role in successful pregnancy outcome. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to analyze the association of various ultrasound parameters of endometrial receptivity, including endometrial thickness, morphology and blood flow on the day of Beta HCG injection to predict outcome in IUI Cycles.

Aim of the study is to assess the predictive value of endometrial thickness, morphology and vasculature using two-dimensional Doppler ultrasound and Transvaginal Sonography after IUI.

Methodology: Prospective Non randomized Open labeled Clinical Study in women undergoing IUI cycle at Government Maternity Hospital, Sri Venkateswara Medical College, Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh. The study was conducted from 1st October 2021 to 30 September 2022.

Results and Conclusion: In the present study, women with EMT 7-10 mm had higher pregnancy rates compared to EMT 10-14 mm. Women with endometrial blood flow in Zone 3 had higher pregnancy rates than Zone 1. Overall pregnancy rate in present study was 9.8%. Higher pregnancy rates were observed when the duration of infertility was <5 years, and the TMSC was between 10 and 20 million. Pregnancy rates decreased with advancing male and female age. Better pregnancy rates were observed in patients with anovulation and malefactor infertility. Most pregnancies occur within the first 3 IUI cycles, after which couples are counselled regarding further assisted Reproductive techniques such as IVF.

Keywords: Infertility, Semen Analysis, Endometrial parameters, Intra Uterine Insemination.

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Introduction

“Infertility is the inability of a couple to achieve pregnancy over an average period of one year (in a woman under 35 years of age) or 6 months (in a woman above 35 years of age) despite adequate, regular (3-4 times per week), unprotected sexual intercourse. In primary infertility, the couples have never been able to conceive, while in secondary infertility there is difficulty in conceiving after having conceived (either carried the pregnancy to term or had a miscarriage)”. [1,2,3]

A complete infertility work up is done before a treatment plan can be developed. The work up is

streamlined, focused and completed shortly so that treatment can be started expeditiously. [4] The last few decades have witnessed a tremendous and steady progress in the treatment of infertility. Intrauterine insemination (IUI) is such an option. IUI is the treatment of the first choice [5] for couples with unexplained and mild male factor infertility in many countries after expectant management. The rationale behind the use of IUI is to reduce the effect of factors such as “vaginal acidity and cervical mucus hostility”. It gives the benefit of direct deposition of prepared motile

sperms close to the female gamete (oocyte) at the time of ovulation. [6]

The success depends on age, duration and type of infertility, follicular count, semen quality and endometrial receptiveness. Ovulation Induction is generally done with clomiphene, gonadotropin, or letrozole or in combination to achieve adequate follicle development. Once the follicle size is optimal (>18 mm), the human chorionic gonadotropin 5000 IU or Inj. Leuprolide acetate 1 mg is given as a trigger or to mimic an artificial LH surge. The IUI is planned 34–36 hours later. On the day of IUI, the husband's semen sample is processed and it is inseminated into the uterine cavity using a IUI catheter. [7]

Successful implantation during IUI requires receptive endometrium. It becomes an absolute necessity to evaluate the uterus and endometrium by high-resolution ultrasound Doppler, a simple non-invasive tool; In various studies, Successful pregnancy is associated with Normal Endometrial thickness (EMT), Presence of triple line endometrium and good blood flow to the endometrium; Most studies reveal successful pregnancy can be achieved with endometrial thickness ranging 7-14mm. However, a meta-analysis in a study conducted by Craciunas L et al showed the predictive ability of endometrial thickness for clinical pregnancy was low. [8] Endometrium with Pattern A on the day of hCG administration has been extensively reported to have a positive relationship with clinical outcomes than pattern B or C endometrium. [9,10] The measurement of endometrial blood flow had played an important role in the expectation of pregnancy outcome. [11] Some authors reported absent endometrial vascularization was associated with significantly lower pregnancy rate and some concluded endometrial blood flow did not significantly affect pregnancy rate. [12-15]

Little progress has been achieved regarding clinical integration in terms of diagnostic tests and treatments for suboptimal endometrial receptivity. [16,17] Studies on endometrial parameters in IUI cycles are insufficient to predict their role in successful pregnancy outcome. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to analyze the association of various ultrasound parameters of endometrial receptivity, including endometrial thickness, morphology and blood flow on the day of Beta HCG injection to predict outcome in IUI Cycles.

Aim: The aim of the study is to assess the predictive value of endometrial thickness, morphology and vasculature using two-dimensional Doppler ultrasound and Transvaginal Sonography after IUI.

Objectives: To calculate the predictive value of endometrial thickness, Endometrial morphology, Endometrial vasculature in terms of pregnancy rate in outcome of Success of IUI.

Methodology:

Study design: Prospective Non randomized Open labeled Clinical Study in women undergoing IUI cycle.

Study setting: Government Maternity Hospital, Sri Venkateswara Medical College, Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh.

Study duration: The study was conducted from 1st October 2021 to 30 September 2022.

Study Population: Women with infertility attending Gynecology OP, Government maternity Hospital, Tirupathi. The prevalence of couples with infertility attending gynecology op in GMH is about 30%.

Sample size: The sample size was calculated as 30 infertile couples with unexplained primary or secondary and mild male factor infertility attending the Gynecology outpatient department during the study period was included in the study. The sample size was calculated using the formula $4PQ/d^2$ where P was Prevalence, Q was 100-P, d was precision, p is taken as 13%, d is taken as 20%.

Inclusion criteria: Couples with Infertile women in age group 19-39 years; clinically and radiologically unexplained primary and secondary infertility; Mild Male factor infertility; unilateral tubal obstruction; polycystic ovarian disease.

Exclusion criteria: Patients who are unable to give written and informed consent.

Demographic data, detailed history, examination was done and recorded. Per speculum examination- to exclude local pathology; Bimanual examination- for position, size, shape, consistency, mobility, tenderness of uterus and its appendages; Examination of external genitalia was done in women, distribution of hair and development of secondary sexual characters was noted. In men, it was done only when warranted and was done by the urologist.

Investigations relating to infertility: Semen analysis of Husband; Transvaginal Sonography (Base line scan); Hysterosalpingography/ Sonosalpingography and/or laparoscopy to confirm normal Uterine anatomy and tubal patency; Thyroid profile; Prolactin levels in case of irregular cycles, Detailed general and reproductive history was taken in the presence of both.

Ovulation induction was done with Tablet Letrozole (Letroz) 2.5mg and follicular monitoring was done. Endometrial pattern was noted as either

triple-line (described as hypoechoic endometrium surrounded by hyperechoic zones) or non-triple-line type B/ C endometrium. After then, Doppler function of the ultrasound machine is used to evaluate the endo-subendometrial blood flow or vascularization and is either, zone I in which the blood flow reached only subendometrial region, zone II in which the blood flow reached the outer hyper-echoic region or zone III in which the blood flow reached the inner hypo-echoic zone. The follicular rupture was diagnosed by the disappearance of leading follicle; Mature follicle with development of internal echoes; Presence of fluid in the pouch of Douglas. Intrauterine insemination was done after the rupture of the follicle or 36 hrs after HCG injection, whichever was earlier. [18]

Ethical Issues: All the study subjects were informed in detail about all aspects of the study,

and consent was obtained. No funding was obtained from any sources. Laboratory investigations at the government setups were used, and no extra cost was imposed on patients. Confidentiality was maintained. Permission from relevant authorities was taken. There were no conflicts of interest.

Statistics: The primary outcome variables were expressed in terms of rate (%).

The data maintenance and statistical analysis was done using Microsoft Excel software and Epi Info version 7.0. Categorical variables and were compared for significant differences using the Chi-square test. P value of <0.05 was considered to be significant.

Results

Table 1: Pregnancy Rate per Cycle

Total Number of Cycles	81
Total Number of Couples	33
Pregnancy After IUI	8
The PR (Pregnancy Rate) Per Cycle Of IUI	9.8%

Table 2: Distribution of the Couples having Pregnancy According to Number of IUI Cycles

Number of IUI Cycles	Number of couples	Total number of IUI cycles	Cycles resulting in pregnancy	PR per cycle (%)
1	3	3	1	33.3
2	12	24	3	12.5
3	18	54	4	7.4
Total	33	81	8	9.8

Table 3: Outcomes of Pregnancy after IUI

Outcomes	Number of Pregnancies(n=8)	Percentage per Cycle (%)
Spontaneous abortion	1	1.2%
Continuing pregnancy at end of the study		
<28weeks	5	6.1%
>28weeks	2	2.4

In the present study Urban (15/33) and rural (18/33) distribution of the couples was almost equal. As per the Modified Kuppaswamy scale, the study subjects were placed in five socio-economic classes. Most of the couples 17/33 (51.5%) in our study belonged to the socio-economic class III. In the present study most of the women are overweight (16/33) 48.48% followed by normal weight (12/33) 36.36%. Maximum number of pregnancies occurred in women with normal BMI.

Table 4: Distribution of the Women According to Past Obstetric History

Past Obstetric History	Number of Women (n=33)	Percentage (%)
Primary infertility	21	63.36
Secondary infertility		
Spontaneous abortion	9	27.27
Previous live child	3	9.09

In patients with primary infertility 6/21 patients conceived with a pregnancy rate of 28.5% and in secondary infertility 2/12 conceived with a pregnancy rate of 16.6%.

Table 5: IUI Outcome According to Age of Women

Age(years)	Number of women (n=33)	Total number of IUI cycles (n=81)	Number of pregnancy after IUI (n=8)	PR per cycle(%)
20-25	4	9	2	22.2
26-30	12	26	4	15.6
31-35	16	43	2	4.6
36-40	1	3	-	-

Table 6: IUI Outcome According to Age of Men

Age (years)	Number of men (n=33)	Total number of IUI cycle (n=81)	Number of Pregnancy after IUI (n=8)	PR per cycle (%)
<25	2	6	1	16.67
26-30	5	12	2	16.67
31-35	11	27	3	11.11
36-40	13	32	1	3.13
>40	2	4	-	-

Table 7: IUI Outcome According to Duration of Infertility

Duration of infertility (years)	Number of couples (n=33)	Number of IUI cycles (n=81)	Number of pregnancy after IUI (n=8)	PR per cycle (%)
1-3	4	10	2	20
4-5	16	43	4	9.3
6-10	12	26	2	7.69
>10	1	2	-	-

Thus, in present study, with increased duration of infertility, the chance of conception after IUI decreased. Maximum pre rate was observed in couples with duration of infertility 1-3 years, no pregnancy was observed in couples having infertility > 10 years.

Table 8: IUI Outcome According to Cause of Infertility

Type of Infertility	Number of couples(N=33)	Total number of IUI cycles (n=81)	Number of pregnancy after IUI (n=8)	PR per cycle(%)
Male subfertility	8	20	2	10
PCOS*	9	24	3	12.5
Combined factors	7	16	1	6.25
Unexplained infertility	9	21	2	9.5

Regular cycles are seen in 18/33 women and 15 patients had irregular cycles. Most of the women had average blood loss (18/33), scanty flow is seen in 13 patients and 2 patients had excessive flow. Thus most of the women had a normal pattern of menstrual cycle length and flow.

During initial evaluation of the infertile couples, the semen of the male partners, collected after 3 days of abstinence, was analyzed according to WHO reference values. Thus most of the men had Normal sperm count (48.48%), normal motility (72.72%) and normal morphology (66.6%).

Thus, IUI success is related to the initial sperm count. Apparently, with initial sperm density 10-20 million/ml gave better results than with ≥ 20 million/ml. It may be explained by the fact that with normal sperm density, other infertility factors may play a dominant role affecting the overall success of IUI. The initial sperm morphology also influences the success of IUI. Sperm morphology with 10-15% normal forms had better results than

sperm morphology of <10% and > 15%.

Pregnancy rate was higher when initial parameters were sperm density- 10-20 x 10^6 /ml; 10-15% sperms had normal morphology; and <50% sperms had normal motility, explaining that IUI success rate is good for mild male factor infertility.

After semen preparation, in each cycle of IUI, the prepared sample is examined under microscope to determine the IMSC. In most of the cases, the IMSC was $\geq 20 \times 10^6$. The relationship between inseminating motile sperm count (IMSC) in each cycle and the outcome of IUI was analyzed and found that with increase in IMSC, the likelihood of success of IUI increases. Maximum pregnancy rates are observed in patients with IMSC 10-20 million/ ml.

In present study Letrozole 2.5mg was used in all patients. Pregnancy rate per cycle with Letrozole Induction in 8/33 was 9.8%. The insemination was scheduled 34-36 hours after HCG injection, follicular rupture on the day of IUI noted and pregnancy

rate was better in patients with follicular rupture 10.2%.

Table 9: IUI Outcome According to Endometrial Thickness, Morphology, blood flow

Endometrial Thickness (mm)	Number of IUI-Cycles (n=81)	Number of Pregnancy (n=8)	PR Per Cycle(%)
<7	13	1	7.69
7-10	42	5	11.9
10-14	26	2	7.69
>14	-		
Endometrial Morphology			
A (tripleline)	56	8	9.8%
B (isoechoicendometrium)	17	-	-
C (Entirely homogeneouslyhyperechoic)	8	-	-
Endometrial Blood Flow			
Zone1	12	-	-
Zone2	23	2	8.69
Zone3	46	6	13

After IUI, the women are observed for any complications, both early and late. Most common was the transient pain during insemination, which was most common in the first cycle and mostly subsided with proper explanation, counseling and emotional support. There was no vasovagal response. Two women developed post-IUI infections characterized by late onset pain and irregular bleeding, which responded to analgesics and antibiotics. One patient had mild symptoms of OHSS (abdominal discomfort) and symptoms subsided with treatment. One patient had spontaneous abortion at 14 weeks gestational age. Thus, most of the complications were mild and transient.

Discussion

Despite revolutionary advances in the field of assisted reproduction such as invitro fertilization (IVF), intrauterine insemination (IUI) remains an inexpensive, noninvasive, and effective first-line therapy for selected patients with cervical factor, mild male factor, unexplained infertility, infertility due to ejaculatory disorders, ovarian dysfunction and even for tubal factor. Several advances in the type of stimulation protocols, gonadotropins, sperm preparation techniques, and ultrasound monitoring have led to promising success rates with IUI. The success rate of IUI depends on various factors like age of the couple, particularly the women; duration and type of infertility; initial seminal parameters; ovarian response; IMSC (inseminating motile sperm count) and endometrial Sonographic parameters. These were evaluated in the present study.

As this study included only a small number of cases in a short period of time, the interpretation of results were done carefully. In 33 couples, a total of 81 cycles of ovarian stimulation with Letrozole 2.5mg followed by IUI is done. Out of 81 cycles, 8 cycles were successful. Out of 8 patients who conceived, one patient had second trimester abortion at

14 weeks gestational age. Ombelet et al., [19] 2009 reported that the mean pregnancy rate per IUI cycle is 10-18%, Kamath et al., [20] reported pregnancy rate per cycle is 8.75% and in most of the literature it is around 10%. In the present study, it was 9.8% and miscarriage rate was 1.2% which was consistent with other studies. In the present study we analyzed that continuing IUI for three cycles resulted in acceptable pregnancy rates; other prognostic factors had a limited impact on these pregnancy rates. In present study reported results are comparable to two previous studies (Tomlinson et al., [21] 1996; Schorsch et al., [22] 2013). The fact that in present study pregnancy rates are somewhat lower might be explained by the fact due to limited use of gonadotropins compared to other studies.

In the present study, women were in the reproductive age group 19-39 years. The mean \pm SD in Non-pregnant patients is 29.62 ± 3.69 and pregnant patients is 28.75 ± 2.72 . In the present study, the pregnancy rates in the age group 20-25 years, 26-30 years, 31-35 years were 22.22%, 15.6%, 4.6% respectively and no pregnancy was reported in the age group 36-40 years. The probability of pregnancy in subjects being over 30 years old was reported to be less than 30 years old and maximum pregnancy rate was observed in 21-25 year old age group although the difference is not statistically significant (P 0.54) Similar pregnancy rates were observed in studies conducted by Schorsch M et al, Dasgupta et al where pregnancy rates were high in age group 21-25 years and 26-30 years.

In the present study, men were in the reproductive age group 19-39 years. In the present study Pregnancy rates are equal in age groups 21-25 years and 26-30 years which were 16.67 and 16.67 respectively. As age increased, the chance of success of IUI decreased. There is no statistically significant difference in age group of males in Non-pregnant and pregnant groups. Less success of IUI was noted in men with age group > 35 years, mostly due to

age factor affecting the seminal parameters and the difference is not statistically significant (P Value 0.60). Similar pregnancy rates were observed in studies conducted by Dasgupta et al., [23] 2012 in 153 IUI Cycles where pregnancy rates were high in men < 30 years old compared to men > 30 years old.

In the present study Most of the women were Overweight 48.48% followed by normal BMI 36.36 %, underweight 9.09% and 2 women 6.06% are obese were included in the study with mean \pm SD 24.01 \pm 7.7kg. Pregnancy rates were found to be high in underweight women 33.33% than normal BMI 25%, the difference observed due to less number of IUI cycles conducted in underweight women than normal BMI women. Pregnancy rate of 16.6% is observed in overweight women. No statistically significant difference was observed between the groups (P value 0.39).

In the present study 63.36% (21/33) of women were having primary infertility and 36.64% (12/33) of women were having secondary infertility. 28.5% (6/21) of women with primary infertility and 16.6% (2/12) of women with secondary infertility achieved pregnancy and difference observed between the two groups were analyzed through Chi-square test and it showed no statistically significant difference between two groups. (P value 0.59). Earlier studies also reported similar pregnancy rates. Kamath et al., [20] 2010 in the prospective study conducted in 480 IUI Cycles reported pregnancy rate of 8.93% in patients with primary infertility and 12.6% in patients with secondary infertility.

In the present study maximum number of patients 48.48% have 4-5 years of infertility, followed by 36.36% with 6-10 years, 12.12% of couples have 1-3 years of infertility and 3.03% of couples have >10 years of infertility with mean \pm SD 5.6 \pm 2.22 and the pregnancy rates observed in them are 9.3%, 7.69%, 20% respectively and no pregnancy was observed in couples with >10 years infertility. The average duration of infertility period was 5.12 \pm 1.64 years in pregnant women and 5.83 \pm 2.4 in non-pregnant women; independent t-test showed no significant difference between them (P value 0.44). Earlier studies also found a significant decline in the success of IUI therapy as the duration of infertility increased. Studies conducted by masrouf et al [24] Kamath et al [20] and Tomlinson et al [21], also suggest that with increasing duration of infertility, IUI as an option appears to be less-effective.

Patients were also evaluated in terms of causes of infertility and according to the results, 8 couples (24.24%) had male factor infertility, 9 patients (27.27%) had polycystic ovaries, 7 patients (21.21%) had combined factors and 9 (27.27%) couples had unexplained infertility. Pregnancy rate

observed was 10% in couples with male factor infertility, 12.5% in patients with PCOS, 6.25% in patients with combined factors and 9.5% in patients with unexplained infertility. Among indications for IUI, the success rate was higher in PCOS and male factor infertility patients as compared with unexplained infertility and lowest in patients with combined factors, although the difference did not reach statistical significance. (P value 0.848). The pregnancy rate in the present study for male factor infertility was marginally lower than that in previously reported studies. Similar pregnancy rates were observed in studies conducted by Dasgupta et al 23 and Kamath et al [20]. The IMSC is an important prognostic factor for IUI success. A universal threshold level above which IUI can be performed with acceptable pregnancy rates has not been determined yet. However, IUI success may be impaired in couples with total motile sperm count (TMSC) <10million, sperm motility<50%, <4% normal spermatozoa, inseminating motile sperm count (IMSC) < 1 million, necessitating alternative therapy. [19]

In the present study among 33 men, majority of men have sperm count>20 million/ml (48.48%), 39.39% men have sperm count 10-20 million/ml and 12.12% of men have sperm count < 5 million/ml. Pregnancy rate of (11.9%)when the IMSC was > 20 million and a similar pregnancy rate of (11.54%) was observed when IMSC was in the range of 5–10 million and no pregnancy was observed when the TMSC was <5 million. Similar pregnancy rates were observed In studies conducted by Kamath et al20and Dasgupta et al [23] and wainer et al [25] there was no statistically significant difference.

In the present study,ultrasonography parameters like EMT, morphology and vasculature are measured on the day of hCG injection and their role in outcome of success of IUI cycles were analyzed. Out of 81 IUI cycles studied, EMT < 7mm was found in 13 cycles (16.04%), 7-10 mm in 42 cycles (51.8%) and 10-14 mm in 26 cycles (32.09%). High rates of pregnancy 11.9% per cycle were observed in patients with EMT 7-10 mm followed by 7.69% and 7.69%with EMT 10-14mm and < 7mm respectively. In the present study, the thinnest endometrial lining for successful ongoing pregnancy was 6.2mm and maximum number of conceptions occurred when the thickness was 7–10 mm and the overall clinical pregnancy rate was 9.8% per cycle. Two groups of pregnant and non-pregnant patients were compared in regard to EMT. Data analysis done using Chi-square test showed no significant differences in EMT between two groups (P=0.817). According to the results of the present study, EMT lacks the potential of predicting the success of IUI cycles.

Habidzadeh et al [25] in a study conducted in 680

IUI cycles, In 36.2% of patients EMT (ET) was ≤ 6 mm and in 59.4% it was $6 < ET \leq 10$ mm and in 4.4% it was > 10 mm. Pregnancy rate was 12.5%. Pregnancy rate in all age ranges with $ET \leq 6$ mm and $6 < ET \leq 10$ mm was 8.9% and 15.6% respectively ($p < 0.05$). Pregnancy rate in all age ranges in $ET > 10$ mm was zero. Dasgupta et al [23] in a study conducted in 153 IUI Cycles, noted clinical pregnancy rates as 7.69% in patients with $EMT < 7$ mm, 10.84% in patients with $EMT 7-10$ mm and 8.51% in patients with $EMT 10-14$ mm. No pregnancy is observed in patients with < 7 mm and > 14 mm. Masrour et al., [24] in a prospective study conducted in IUI cycles in 100 patients EMT was compared in pregnant and non pregnant; in the group of pregnant women, 21 (58.3%) subjects with less than 7mm, 14 cases (38.9%) with EMT between 7 and 14, and one case of more than 14 thickness; in the non- pregnant group, and 23 (35.9%) patients with EMT of less than 7 and 41 (64.1%) patients had a thickness between 7-14. Data analysis using Chi-square test showed significant differences in EMT between two groups ($p = 0.029$).

Induvadana T. M et al., [26] (2022) in a study conducted in 37 IUI Cycles in Government maternity hospital in Tirupati, noted that all pregnancies occurred (3/37) cycles in patients with $EMT 7-13$ mm.

In the present study Triple line pattern is found in 56 cycles 69.13%, type B and type C endometrium in 17 cycles 20.9% and 8 cycles 9.87% respectively. Clinical pregnancy rate of 9.8% is observed. Successful pregnancy is reported only in patients with type A (Triple line pattern) 8/56 cycles and no pregnancy was observed in patients with type B or C endometrium. Data analysis, through Chi-square test, also showed no significant difference between groups in the pattern of endometrial ultrasound ($P = 0.85$).

Masrour et al., [24] in their study In pregnant group, 20 cases (55.5%) were represented as pattern A, 13 cases (36.1%) as pattern B, and 3 cases (8.4%) as pattern C. Data analysis, through Chi-square test, also showed no significant difference between groups in the pattern of endometrial ultrasound ($p = 0.198$).

Tsai and his colleagues [27] in a prospective study conducted in 110 IUI cycles which resulted in 16 clinical pregnancies, pregnancy rates in triple line and nontriple line groups were 17.9% and 6.3%, respectively ($P = 0.22$) and stated that women, whose ultrasound showed triple-line patterns, became pregnant more frequently than women without this pattern.

In the present study Out of 81 IUI cycles studied, EBF in Zone 1 is observed in 12 cycles, Zone 2 in 23 cycles and Zone 3 in 46 cycles. According to the study a higher pregnancy rate was observed when

the blood flow to the endometrium was in Zone 3 51.8% (6/46) compared to Zone 2 14.8% (2/23) and no pregnancy was observed in patients with EBF in Zone 1.

According to the results of the present study, EBF in women who became pregnant through IUI cycles is significantly different from that of those women who did not get pregnant. The women who experienced a more successful cycle had higher EBF compared to non-pregnant women. The difference observed between pregnant and non-pregnant patients was analyzed by Chi square test and found no statistically significant difference ($P = 0.819$)

Masrour et al., [24] 2019 in a prospective study conducted in 100 patients undergoing IUI cycles observed that in the pregnant women group, 21 patients (58.3%) were diagnosed with a meaningful blood flow and 15 subjects (41.7%) with a mild blood flow; in the non-pregnant women group, 17 patients (26.2%) were diagnosed with no flow, 36 patients (56.2%) with a mild flow, and 11 of them (17.2%) with a meaningful flow. Data analysis using the Chi-square test demonstrated a meaningful difference between the two groups as regards the endometrial blood flow ($P = 0.00$)

Zaidi et al [28] analyzed EMT, endometrial morphology, and presence or absence of sub-endometrial or intra-endometrial color flow in 96 infertile patients undergoing IVF cycles. The results of the study obtained on the day of HCG administration were related to the pregnancy rates. The overall pregnancy rate was 32.3%, and there was no remarkable difference between pregnant (P) and non- pregnant groups (NP) regarding EMT. The pregnancy rates were not significantly different for different morphological patterns of endometrium ($p > 0.05$). The absence of EBF was associated with the failure of implantation ($p < 0.05$).

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